

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PLA-BAMBOO FIBERS GREEN COMPOSITE

F. Ramirez^{1*}, M. Gonzalez², N. Barrera², S. Castellanos¹

¹Civil & Environmental Engineering Department, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

² Chemistry Engineering Department, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

* Corresponding author (framirez@uniandes.edu.co)

Abstract

Guadua angustifolia kunth (GAK) is a giant bamboo naturally found in South America. It is a renewable and sustainable material with very rapid growth. The GAK fibers are potentially suitable for reinforcement of composite materials because of its physical properties, good adhesion and resistance to the PLA polymer. This kind of composite has a potential to replace wood based products in the construction sector. In this study, GAK fibers were extracted and the mechanical properties of GAK fibers-PLA composites were determined. It was found the maximum temperature for processing the composite material and the length of GAK for good. The GAK fibers were extracted with the kraft process and were manufactured with PLA pellets compound using an internal mixer. Composite samples were obtained by varying the fiber size and volume proportions. It was found that the use of GAK fibers has a potential for reinforcing composite materials and the inclusion of small fibers proportions improves the composite stiffness and strength.

Keywords: *Green Composites, Natural Fibers, Biodegradable Matrix, Mechanical Properties*

1 Introduction

Polymeric materials reinforced with lignocellulosic fibers, mainly competing in the market with compression molded wood, especially in the application of story or profiles in the civil construction sector [1].

In Latin American countries, the introduction of these materials requires adaptation to agro-fiber vegetables local industry. Guadua angustifolia Kunth (GAK) is a giant bamboo species abundant in America. It is characterized by sustainable and renewable material, with periods growing very fast compared to the wood.

Furthermore, it is a fibrous material high structural strength and good performance, so it is used in construction sector. However, the top part of the GAK, which has the highest concentration of fibers, is discarded due to its small diameter.

Nevertheless, these fibers have mechanical and physical properties that make them potentially suitable for reinforcement of composite materials, giving an add value to this part of the plant.

On the other hand, polylactide (PLA) is a degradable polyester derived from renewable resources such a cornstarch and sugarcane, among others.

In particular, natural fiber composites have taken an unusual acceptance due to their low cost, and its renewable resource, with excellent production processes achieves a good balance with regard to its mechanical properties, making them comparable to references of artificial fiber reinforced materials and compete in the sector construction with wood, especially in the manufacture of flooring and profiles, presenting an accelerated growth.

In the present work, fibers from the top part of the GAK were extracted through a chemical digestion process, then the extracted fiber bundles were characterized, and PLA composites with different GAK fiber lengths and volume fractions were prepared and tested.

2 GAK Fiber Extraction and Properties

The bamboo species used for the investigation was *Guadua angustifolia* from Cauca Valley, Colombia. This region is located at 1100 meters over the sea level and 22°C of temperature. The 4-year-old bamboo culms used are from the upper part of the plant with external diameter that varies from 4.5 to 10 cm and culm wall from 0.4 to 1.8 cm thick. For the digestion process the GAK culms were cut into chips of 8 to 10 cm long, 0.5 to 3.0 cm wide and the thickness between 0.5 and 2.0 cm at the aim of getting a better reagent soaked in the digestion. GAK fibers were extracted at the Environmental Laboratory of Universidad de los Andes, Colombia.

2.1 Fibers extraction

The extraction kraft process was performed using and autoclave with a temperature of 127°C and 150 KPa pressure during 4 hours. This process employs sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and sodium sulfide (Na₂S). The digestion was performed with an effective alkali EA of 20%, a sulfidity S of 50%, and a hydro module HM of 4. The pH was adjusted to 7 washing the fibers with acetic acid.

Once the fibers were extracted, they were cut and classified into two different sizes: short fibers with length between 0.1 and 0.25 mm and medium fibers 0.25 – 4.76 mm long. The fibers obtained were dried at 105°C over 24 hours.

3 PLA-GAK Fibers Composite

Composites were prepared using two different fiber lengths, short (S) and medium (M), and three different fiber weight fractions 10%, 20 %, and 40% resulting in six different composite formulations: S10, S20, S40, M10, M20, and M40 respectively.

3.1 Composites preparation.

Composite were prepared by dry mixing at room temperature for 3 minutes in a high speed mixer. Previously the fibers and PLA were dried in a forced convection oven Nemmert iP20 for 24 hours at 65 ° C. The compounds were processed in the internal mixer Brabender Plasti-Corder PLE-331 where evaluated the thermal stability characteristics were determined and processability process mixtures.

These were carried out at constant temperature of 180 ° C and a speed 50rpm for 10 minutes. The obtained composite is then cooled down and milled into pellets.

3.2 Mechanical characterization.

The compounds obtained were characterized by tensile and bending according to ASTM D638 and D790 respectively, in a universal machine Instron 3367. Additionally Izod impact strength in a machine TMI was determined, following ASTM D256 standard. The test specimens were obtained by compression molding at 180°C taking a total time of 25 minutes, 10 minutes for preheating, 5 minutes for compression, and 10 minutes for cooling.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Thermal stability of fibers.

The thermal stability of GAK was determined by thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA), where was possible confirm the stability of fibers until 250°C. This is a good behavior taking into account the temperature at which the composites are processed. The thermogravimetric curve is shown in the figure 1. Additionally, the tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of the fiber is from 233.6 MPa and 20.6 GPa, respectively [2]. The mechanical properties of the fibers are comparable to values of GAK resistance glass fibers, so GAK fibers are a good alternative to synthetic fibers [2].

An important parameter to consider is the influence of the extraction process of the fiber in the composite properties, since this is done in an alkaline medium, which helps to remove the lignin content and improve the adhesion between the fiber and the matrix. Thus, the fiber obtained has a surface modification, allowing greater the homogeneity in the compound.

4.2 Mechanical Characterization.

Seven tensile tests were performed for each composite formulation. Based on the results of these tests the elasticity modulus and strength were obtained. Average results are shown in Figures 2 and 3. It can be seen that the composite modulus of

elasticity increases not only with the fiber volume fraction but also with the fiber length. These results are expected since the stiffness of the fibers is higher than that of the PLA matrix.

On the other hand, the strength of the composite is lower than that of the PLA matrix, and also increases with fiber volume fraction. The tensile tests showed that the short fiber formulation 40% proved to be the best due to its high modulus of elasticity in which we determined the material stiffness and breaking load of the composite.

This behavior could be attributed to the better dispersity of the fibers in a polymer matrix [3], increasing the adhesion between the interfaces. Considering the potential applications for use, formulation of 40% short fiber is ideal for application in sheet flooring by having a low percentage of elongation and high load bearing. It can also be applied in auto parts recorded high rigidity [4].

However, there are no significant differences between composites with different fiber lengths but equal fiber volume fraction.

Composites were also subjected to seven bending tests for each formulation. The resulting average moduli of rupture are illustrated in Figure 4. A reduction in bending strength is observed in comparison to PLA. A possible explanation is that although the fibers produce an increase in tensile strength, they may cause a reduction in compression strength [5]. If this reduction is high enough the bending strength of the composite would be also reduced.

Finally, seven impact tests were also performed on the composite for each formulation. Average results are shown in Figure 5. The composite impact strength increased in comparison to that of the PLA as expected. It was found that the impact resistance is higher for all fiber reinforced formulations compared to PLA polymer matrix.

An increase in impact value of 28% relative to the polymer matrix was reached. This is attributed to

increase as the fiber content increases the stiffness of the compound [7].

The optimum value is obtained for the composite with a fiber volume fraction of 20% for both fiber lengths.

The effect of stiffening fibers in the compound can be seen in the dramatic decrease in percent elongation. In Figure 6 shows that this effect is most noticeable when short fibers are used, that mean, a lower percentage of short fibers in the polymer matrix provide increased ductility. Moreover, it does not happen in the same way with medium fiber and in this case is obtained in an optimum average fiber formulation 20%. These results are related to those obtained in the impact and flexural tests.

However, despite the stiffening which gives the fiber, torque levels and fusion times shown by the compounds developed doesn't change significantly, and allow these to be processed on conventional equipment. Figures 7 and 8 show curves obtained for formulations torque limits, ie low short fiber content and high fiber content media respectively.

5 Conclusions

In the present study the use of two biodegradable materials, GAK fibers and PLA, in a composite was explored for different fiber lengths and fiber volume fractions. Results indicate a tensile stiffening effect of the fibers in the PLA matrix, but a small reduction in tensile and bending strength. The composite mechanical properties demonstrate its potential use in non-structural elements. Further research is required not only to determine the optimum PLAGAK fibers composites, but also to explore its possible application for structural elements.

5 References

- [1]Biagiotti, Jerico, Fiori, S y Torre, Luigi. 2004, *Mechanical properties of polypropylene matrix composites reinforced with natural fibers*, Polymer Composites, 2004, pp. 26–36.
- [2]Deshpande, Abhijit y Rao, Bhaskar. 2000, *Extraction of bamboo fibers and their use as reinforcement in polymeric composites*, Journal of applied polymer science, 2000, pp76:83–92.

[3]Gonzalez, Valadez y Cervantes, J.M. 1998, *Effect of fiber surface treatment on the fiber–matrix bond strength of natural fiber reinforced composites*, Centro de Investigación Científica de Yucatán, 1998.

[4]Isaac, Daniel y Ishai, Ori. 2006. *Engineering mechanics of composite materials*, Oxford University press, 2006.

[5]Jain, Seema y Kumar, Rakesh. 1992, *Mechanical behaviour of bamboo and bamboo composite*, Journal of Materials Science, 1992, pp 4598–4604.

[6]Kim, Pickering. 2008. *Properties performance of natural fibre composites*. Cambridge Woodhead Publishing Limited, 2008.

[7]Klyosov, Anatole, 2007, *Wood plastic composites*. Hoboken, New Jersey, John Wiley & Sons.

[8]Okubo, Kazuya, Fujii, Toru y Yamamoto, Yuzo. 2004. *Development of bamboo based polymer composites and their mechanical properties*, Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2004, pp 377–383.

[9]Sreekumar, P. 2008, *Matrices for natural-fibre reinforced composites*, Cambridge: Properties and performance of natural-fiber composites, pp 67–126.

Fig 1 Thermal stability of GAK fibers.

Fig 2 Composite average modulus of elasticity.

Fig 3 Composite average strength.

Fig 4. Composite average modulus of rupture.

Fig 5. Composite average impact strength.

Fig 8. Torque curve medium fiber 40%.

Fig 6. Elongation at break.

Fig 7. Torque curve short fiber 10%.